

RESILIENCE Statutes and Technical and Scientific Description

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Version Number	Date	Status	Name	Summary of Main Changes
00.01	01/10/2025	DRAFT	Initial Draft	
00.02	29/10/2025	DRAFT	First Revised Text	D1.1 RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws and protocols - 1st draft is adapted to the template offered in the ERIC guidelines published in March 2025
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Distribution List

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1 Introduction

The RESILIENCE PPP GA n. 101079792 indicates that D1.2 collects all documents requested for the establishment of the ERIC in their latest version before the signature of the Member Countries. Such a description reflected the plan presented in the RESILIENCE PPP to apply for the establishment of the RESILIENCE ERIC by the end of the project.

The RESILIENCE (Interim) General Assembly approved the draft of the statutes included in D1.1 RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws and protocols - 1st draft on December 2nd, 2024, after the submission of the document as a RESILIENCE PPP deliverable and the closure of Reporting Period 2.

Since then, the development of RESILIENCE PPP proceeded as expected, but the instability of the governance at the CNR in Italy, which is the body through which the funds directed to the RESILIENCE ERIC should transit and guaranteeing their allocation in its yearly budget, resulted in an interruption of the preliminary activities (e.g. letter of commitment) requested by the Italian government to start the negotiations procedures for the establishment of the ERIC.

For this reason, at the end of the RESILIENCE PPP RESILIENCE will not be able to submit the ERIC proposal.

Nonetheless, in the past year a) the European Commission published a new version of the ERIC Practical Guidelines, and b) feedback was collected on the first draft of the Statutes and Technical and Scientific Description, so this document is an advanced version of a text that could be a starting point for the work related to the ERIC establishment.

2 Background

The *ERIC practical guidelines. Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium* published in 2025 by the European Commission offer to potential ERIC applicants all indications concerning the procedures to follow and the documentation to prepare in order to apply for the recognition of the ERIC legal status.

The guidelines list the documents that members of a future ERIC should prepare and agree upon the content to submit the ERIC application, which include:

- Request to the Commission to set up the ERIC
- The draft statutes of the ERIC
- The technical and scientific description of the research infrastructure to be established and operated by the ERIC
- The declaration by the host state recognising the ERIC as an international body and international organisation.
- The declaration of non-EU Member States recognising the legal personality and capacity of the ERIC (if needed)

Therefore, WP1 worked on the documentation that is responsibility of the RI to draft and propose: Draft statutes and the Technical and scientific description.

While the draft of the RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes that is presented here is the result of an elaboration of the previous project deliverable, D1.1 RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws and protocols - 1st draft, the Technical and scientific Description remain the same.

This update is delivered, just like the previous version, in a changing context. The unforeseen developments brought by the NextGenerationEU funding for research Infrastructures in the Italian context and the developments of the relationship between RESILIENCE and other RI's in the SSH domain via the SSHOC governing board and its Pillars, strongly influence the technical setting of the RI, and its service catalogue, which is already published in its beta-version and will be finally delivered as a document by November 30th, 2025. In addition, a "RESILIENCE Transition to Implementation Phase" proposal was submitted on September 17th, 2025 to address the call HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01 (Research Infrastructures 2025) published by the European Commission and ask for its support in allowing the RI to gain more maturity before entering the Implementation Phase – also in light of the challenges and opportunities which emerged during the RESILIENCE PPP – including the difficulties in submitting in due time the ERIC application.

3 Draft of the RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes

CHAPTER 1

ESSENTIAL ELEMENTS

Article 1

Name and statutory seat

1. "Religious Studies Infrastructure: tooLs, Innovation, Experts, coNnections and Centres in Europe is set up as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) under Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 named 'RESILIENCE ERIC'.
2. RESILIENCE ERIC shall have its statutory seat in Palermo, Italy.

Article 2

Task and activities

1. The principal task of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be to establish and operate the RESILIENCE research infrastructure. The ultimate purpose of the RESILIENCE research infrastructure is to serve research by improving infrastructural conditions of research on religion all over Europe, especially by enhancing access to digital as well as physical data on religion and to advanced tools, training, existing research infrastructures and expertise for new, digital, and data-oriented research on religion on a global level.
2. For the purposes of paragraph 1 and in cooperation with the relevant research and study communities RESILIENCE ERIC shall carry out the following activities:
 - a. creation and operation of new methods, instruments, tools and services to better support research on religion by making use of tested and cutting edge information technologies and by stimulating the usage of new technologies in research on religion.
 - b. creation of one point of access to the many distributed sites and institutions of research on religion in Europe which are willing to share resources, data and technologies.
 - c. connection of institutions and facilities with strong competence and experience in digital and data-oriented research methods and which have rich resources for research on religion.
 - d. support to the exchange knowledge, expertise, methodologies and practices across academic disciplines and research domains.
 - e. any other related action necessary to achieve its task.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall pursue its principal task on a non-profit basis. RESILIENCE ERIC may carry out limited economic activities provided that they are closely related to its principal task and that they do not jeopardise the achievement thereof.

Article 3

Duration

RESILIENCE ERIC shall exist for an indefinite period of time.

Article 4

Winding up

1. The winding up of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be decided by the General Assembly in accordance with Article 21.
2. Without undue delay and in any event within ten days after adoption of the decision to wind up RESILIENCE ERIC, RESILIENCE ERIC shall notify the European Commission about the decision.
3. Assets remaining after payment of RESILIENCE ERIC debts shall be apportioned among the members in proportion to their accumulated annual contribution to RESILIENCE ERIC as specified in Annex 2.
4. Without undue delay and in any event within ten days of the closure of the winding up procedure, RESILIENCE ERIC shall notify the Commission thereof.
5. RESILIENCE ERIC shall cease to exist on the day on which the European Commission publishes the appropriate notice in the Official Journal of the European Union.

Article 5

Liability and insurance

1. RESILIENCE ERIC shall be liable for its debts.
2. The members are not jointly liable for the debts of RESILIENCE ERIC.
3. The members' financial liability for the debts of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be limited to their respective annual contribution as specified in Annex 2.
4. RESILIENCE ERIC shall take appropriate insurance to cover the risks specific to the construction and operation of the RESILIENCE RI.

Article 6

Access Policy for users

1. RESILIENCE ERIC shall provide, as much as possible, a wide and unrestricted access to the tools and resources made available through the infrastructure taking into account the sustainability of those resources.
2. Access shall be in principle freely available for use by the scientific and educational community. However, capacity, technical, financial or environmental sustainability reasons may require that some services may be offered with restrictions with the specification of clear conditions.
3. For restricted services offered by RESILIENCE ERIC, where access is requested by academic researchers, it shall be excellence driven. The scientific excellence of project proposals shall be judged in peer reviews by independent experts, and the criteria and procedures shall be decided by the General Assembly, with advice from the Advisory Board. Such criteria shall also take into account that a certain amount of the capacity should be reserved for totally new ideas that may not yet have reached full maturity or widely recognized scientific excellence. The peers shall be selected by the Executive Director in accordance with the evaluation policy.

4. Access for non academic institutions, industry and similar types of specific non-academic users as well may be granted for a fee.
5. Users will need to accept the general terms of service regulating access to the specific resources.
6. Procedures and evaluation criteria shall be made publicly available on RESILIENCE ERIC website.

Article 7

Scientific Evaluation Policy

The activities of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be evaluated annually by the Advisory Board.

Article 8

Dissemination Policy

1. RESILIENCE ERIC shall be a facilitator of research and shall as a general rule encourage the principle as open as possible, as restricted as necessary to research data.
2. RESILIENCE ERIC shall request researchers to make their research results publicly available and to make results generated using the RI available through RESILIENCE ERIC.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall use several channels to reach the target audiences, including web portal, social media, newsletter, workshops, presence in conferences, articles in magazines and daily newspapers.

Article 9

Intellectual Property Rights Policy

1. Intellectual property rights of results created by RESILIENCE ERIC shall belong to RESILIENCE ERIC.
2. Subject to the term of any contract between RESILIENCE ERIC and the users, intellectual property rights created, obtained or developed by users shall be owned by those users.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall adopt a policy on intellectual property rights for approval by the General Assembly.

Article 10

Employment Policy

1. RESILIENCE ERIC employment policy shall be governed by the laws of the country in which staff is employed.
2. The selection procedures for RESILIENCE ERIC staff positions shall be transparent, non-discriminatory and respect equal opportunities. Recruitment and employment shall not be discriminatory.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall adopt an employment policy for approval by the General Assembly.

Article 11

Procurement policy

1. RESILIENCE ERIC shall treat procurement candidates and tenderers from EU Member States as well as ERIC members and observers, equally and without discrimination.
2. Procurement by members and observers concerning RESILIENCE ERIC activities shall be carried out in such a way that due consideration is given to RESILIENCE ERIC needs, technical requirements and specifications issued by the relevant bodies.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall adopt its own procurement rules, which respect to the principles of transparency, non-discrimination and competition, to be approved by the General Assembly, and be made available on RESILIENCE ERIC website.

CHAPTER 2

GENERAL PROVISIONS

Article 12

Definitions

For the purposes of these statutes, the following definitions shall apply:

ERIC Regulation means Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), as amended.

Host Country means Italy.

Implementing Rules means the internal rules, financial rules, rules of procedure and terms of reference adopted by the General Assembly which govern the operation of RESILIENCE ERIC bodies set out in Articles 18-21.

RESILIENCE RI means Religious Studies Infrastructure: tooLs, Innovation, Experts, conNections and Centres in Europe.

Simple Majority means the number of votes cast "for" a decision exceeds 50% of the total number of votes cast "for" and "against" that decision. Abstentions shall not be considered as votes cast.

Two-thirds Majority means the number of votes cast "for" a decision is at least 66.7% of the total number of votes cast "for" and "against" that decision. Abstentions shall not be considered as votes cast.

Unanimous Vote means no votes casted "against" a decision. Abstentions shall not be considered as votes cast.

CHAPTER 3

MEMBERSHIP AND OBSERVER STATUS

Article 13

Membership and representing entity

1. The following entities may become members of RESILIENCE ERIC or may become observers of RESILIENCE ERIC without voting rights:
 - a. Member States of the European Union;
 - b. associated countries (within the meaning of Article 2(c) of the ERIC Regulation).
 - c. third countries other than associated countries;
 - d. intergovernmental organisations.
2. Membership of RESILIENCE ERIC must consist of at least a Member State and two other countries that are either Member States or associated countries.
3. Member States or associated countries shall hold jointly the majority of the voting rights in the General Assembly. The General Assembly shall determine any modification of voting rights that are necessary to ensure that RESILIENCE ERIC complies at all times with that requirement.
4. Any member or observer referred to in paragraph 1(a) to (c) may be represented by one public entity or one private entity with a public service mission, of its own choosing and appointed in accordance with its own rules and procedures. Each member or observer shall inform the General Assembly of any change of its representing entity, of the specific rights and obligations which have been delegated to it or of any other relevant change.
5. The members and observers of RESILIENCE ERIC and their representing entities are listed in Annex 1. Annex 1 shall be kept up to date by the Chair of the General Assembly.

Article 14

Conditions for becoming a member or an observer

1. Entities referred to in Article 13(1) willing to become members of RESILIENCE ERIC shall submit a written application to the Chair of the General Assembly. That application shall describe how the entity will contribute to RESILIENCE ERIC task and activities described in Article 2 and how it will fulfil obligations referred to in Article 16.

The admission of the entities as new members shall be subject to approval by the General Assembly.
2. Entities referred to in Article 13(1) who are willing to contribute to RESILIENCE ERIC but are not yet in a position to join as members, may apply for observer status.

Entities willing to become observers of RESILIENCE ERIC shall submit a written application to the Chair of the General Assembly. That application shall describe how the applicant will contribute to RESILIENCE ERIC tasks and activities described in Article 2 and how it will fulfil obligations referred to in Article 17.

3. Applicants shall be admitted as observers for a two-year period. Observers may reapply for extension of observer status. The admission or re-admission of observers shall be subject to the approval by the General Assembly.

Article 15

Withdrawal of a member or an observer/Termination of membership or observer status

1. Within the first eight years of the establishment of RESILIENCE ERIC no member may withdraw unless the membership has been entered into for a specified shorter period.
2. After the first eight years of the establishment of RESILIENCE ERIC a member may withdraw at the end of a financial year, following a request submitted 12 months prior to the withdrawal.
3. Observers may withdraw at the end of a financial year, following a request submitted 6 months prior to the withdrawal.
4. Members and observers shall fulfil financial and other obligations before their withdrawal can become effective.
5. The General Assembly may terminate membership or observer status if the following conditions are met:
 - a. the member or observer is in serious breach of one or more of its obligations under these statutes;
 - b. the member or observer has failed to rectify such breach within 6 months after it has received notice of the breach in writing.
 - c. The member or observer had been given the right to explain its position to the General Assembly before the General Assembly makes any decision on the issue.

CHAPTER 4

RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF THE MEMBERS AND OBSERVERS

Article 16

Members

1. Rights of members shall include:
 - a. access to RESILIENCE ERIC and all its services to its research community;
 - b. to attend and vote in the General Assembly;
 - c. to shape RESILIENCE ERIC strategy and budget allocation;
 - d. to use RESILIENCE ERIC brand;
 - e. to let its research community participate in RESILIENCE ERIC events, such as workshops, conferences, training courses;
 - f. where relevant, to participate in project proposals where RESILIENCE ERIC acts as the submitting consortium.

2. Each member shall:
 - a. provide the annual contribution in accordance with Annex 2;
 - b. appoint a representing entity in accordance with Article 1 and empower its representing entity with the full authority to vote on all issues raised during the General Assembly and published in the agenda;
 - c. promote adoption of relevant standards;
 - d. provide the necessary technical infrastructure to make access possible;
 - e. create a national consortium for carrying out the national obligations following from these statutes; a consortium may consist of one or more institutions;
 - f. appoint a national coordinator responsible for the national consortium and member of the National Coordinators Committee with voting rights in this committee;
 - g. promote uptake of services among researchers in the member country, and gather user feedback and requirements;
 - h. support centres in the member country by facilitating integration into national and other relevant infrastructures;
 - i. provide the necessary information for reporting to the General Assembly and the European Commission.
3. Members who have joined RESILIENCE ERIC reserving the right to withdraw before the end of the first eight years of the establishment of RESILIENCE ERIC shall pay a higher annual fee as specified in Annex 2.
4. Contributions other than the annual fee to RESILIENCE ERIC may be provided by members individually or jointly in cooperation with other members, observers or third parties. Such contributions may be made in cash or in kind.

Article 17

Observers

1. Rights of observers shall include:
 - a. the right to attend the General Assembly, with no voting rights;
 - b. The right to attend the National Coordinators Committee without a vote;
 - c. the right to be granted access to external and internal RESILIENCE ERIC communication channels to be able to follow latest developments;
 - d. the right for its research community to participate in RESILIENCE ERIC events, such as workshops, conferences, training courses;
 - e. the right for its research community to have access to support from RESILIENCE ERIC in developing relevant systems, processes and services.
2. Each observer shall:
 - a. contribute to the RESILIENCE ERIC by providing expertise in their field of research, services, library and archival resources and/or technologies according to the activities enlisted in Article 2;

- b. appoint a representing entity as mentioned in Article 16 and always keep the General Assembly informed about who the representing entity is;
 - c. appoint a national coordinator responsible for the formation of a national consortium;
 - d. pay the annual fee as specified in Annex 2;
 - e. participate in relevant RESILIENCE activities;
 - f. engage in activities towards national RI-membership.
3. Contributions other than the annual fee to RESILIENCE ERIC may be provided by observers individually or jointly in cooperation with other members, observers or third parties. Such contributions may be made in cash or in kind.
4. An observer shall empower its representing entity to carry out the obligations referred to in Article 17. RESILIENCE ERIC shall enter into a RESILIENCE Observer Agreement with that entity in order to lay down the conditions and specifications under which the obligation shall be fulfilled or the contribution shall be made.

CHAPTER 5

GOVERNANCE

Article 18

General Assembly

1. The General Assembly shall be the governing body of RESILIENCE ERIC and shall be composed of representatives of the members and observers of RESILIENCE ERIC.
2. Each member shall appoint at least one official representative but not more than 2 representatives.
3. Each member shall have one indivisible vote with all votes being of equal value.
4. A member may bring an expert. Each delegation may consequently consist of up to two persons, but the official representative carries the vote.
5. The General Assembly shall meet at least once a year, and shall:
 - a. be responsible for the overall direction and supervision of RESILIENCE ERIC;
 - b. appoint, suspend or dismiss the Executive Director;
 - c. decide on the Strategic Plan, consisting of the annual strategy and the annual budget;
 - d. decide on accession of a new Member or Observer and of the settlement on the conditions of the accession;
 - e. decide on withdrawal of a Member or Observer and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal;
 - f. identify a breach by a Member or Observer of its contractual or ethical obligations;
 - g. declare a Member or Observer to be a Defaulting Member or Observer and the approval of the remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Member or Observer;
 - h. adopt decisions on contributions;
 - i. adopt general bylaws;
 - j. create advisory bodies if deemed necessary and appoint their members;

- k. and decide on any other matter that is necessary to fulfill the tasks of RESILIENCE ERIC statutes.
6. The meetings of the General Assembly shall be convened by the Chair with at least 45 days of notice, and the final agenda shall be circulated at least 15 days before the meeting. Members shall have the right to suggest matters for the agenda up to three weeks before the meeting. A meeting of the General Assembly may be requested by at least 1/3 of the members, and the meeting shall be held as soon as possible, with at least 15 days' notice.
 7. The General Assembly shall elect a Chair by simple majority of the votes. The Chair shall be a member's official representative. The Chair shall be elected for a 24 months term, renewable once.
 8. The General Assembly shall elect a Vice-Chair by simple majority of the votes. The Vice Chair shall be a member's official representative. The Vice Chair shall be elected for a 24 months term, renewable once. The Vice-chair shall substitute the Chair in his/her absence and in case of conflict of interest.
 9. If an official representative cannot attend the General Assembly, the member may authorise another representative from the same member, the national expert or an official representative of another member to vote on its behalf by means of a written and duly signed authorisation, which shall be presented to the Chair by the beginning of the meeting. No representative may bring more than three authorisations.
 10. A quorum of 2/3 of members shall be required for having a valid General Assembly meeting. If the quorum is not met, a second meeting shall be convened within 15 calendar days following a new invitation, with the same agenda. The second meeting shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of members is present or represented.
 11. The General Assembly shall be chaired by the Chair, and in his or her absence by the Vice Chair. The Chair, or a person authorised by the Chair, shall be responsible for updating Annex 1, so there shall be at all times an accurate list of the members, observers and their representing entities.
 12. All decisions shall be passed by simple majority of the votes cast. The following decisions shall require majority of 2/3 of the votes cast
 - a. amendment of the statutes of RESILIENCE ERIC;
 - b. termination of RESILIENCE ERIC;
 - c. termination of membership or observer status;
 - d. assignment of the defaulting partner status;
 - e. adoption of general bylaws;
 - f. suspension or dismissal of the Executive Director;
 - g. decisions related to the amount or calculation of contributions.
 13. Voting shall be conducted by secret ballot if requested by a representative. In case of a tie, the President shall have the casting vote.
 14. The quorum of the General Assembly shall be two thirds of the votes. The representatives may be present in person or by authorisation, as described in Article 8.6. The General Assembly may decide to use technology, such as video conferencing, for meetings.

Article 19

Executive Director

1. The assembly of members shall appoint the Executive Director of RESILIENCE ERIC in accordance with a procedure adopted by the assembly of members and specified in the bylaws.
2. The term for the Executive Director shall be 3 years, with a possibility of an administrative prolongation, meaning a prolongation without competition, of up to two years decided by the General Assembly. At the end of the five-year term or when the appointment can no longer be prolonged, another open call shall be issued.
3. The Executive Director shall be the legal representative of RESILIENCE ERIC.
4. The Executive Director shall carry out the day-to-day management of RESILIENCE ERIC. The Executive Director shall be responsible for the implementation of the decisions taken by the assembly of members.

Article 20

Advisory Board

1. The Advisory Board shall offer professional advice on topics relevant to the RI – scientific, technical, financial, ethical, etc. - and may be asked to issue an opinion on specific topics by any governance body.
2. The Advisory Board shall consist of leading international experts in different fields relevant to the RI. Expertise in different areas of the study of religion and IT, and the communities of use shall be represented in their variety in the Advisory Board.
3. The number of members of the Advisory Board shall be decided by the General Assembly. This number shall not be less than 5.
4. The members of the Advisory Board shall be proposed and appointed by the General Assembly for a term of 4 years. The General Assembly may reappoint them once for the same duration.
5. The Chair of the Advisory Board shall be elected among its members.
6. The Chair shall convene and chair all meetings of the Advisory Board.
7. The by-laws of the Advisory Board shall be based on the general by-laws scheme developed by the Executive Director. The by-laws shall be approved by the Executive Director.
8. The Advisory Board shall meet annually and provide advice and guidance to the General Assembly and all other RESILIENCE bodies on scientific and technical matters.
9. The Advisory Board shall prepare an annual report for the General Assembly on current technological and scientific advancements including recommendations for improving the RESILIENCE infrastructure.

Article 21

National Coordinators Committee

1. It shall be the duty of each member or observer being a country to appoint a national coordinator. The national coordinator shall act as the main liaison between RESILIENCE ERIC and the national consortium.
2. National coordinators from observers will be observers in the National Coordinators' Committee.

3. In the case of countries that are neither Members nor Observers in RESILIENCE, individual institutions are allowed to take part in the National Coordinators Committee with the status of Observers.
4. The Committee shall have the task of advising the assembly of members in regard to the annual Strategic Plan; offering scientific advice to all governance bodies; attending the assembly of members meetings without voting rights; ensuring consistency, coherence and stability of infrastructure services.
5. The Committee reports its findings and recommendations to the Executive Director and collaborates with the Executive Director in the implementation of the decisions taken by the assembly of members. For this purpose, the Executive Director participates in the National Coordinators' Committee meetings.
6. The by-laws of the National Coordinators Committee shall be based on the general by-laws scheme developed by the Executive Director. The by-laws shall be approved by the Executive Director.

Article 22

Third parties

1. In cases where the Executive Director deems it beneficial for RESILIENCE ERIC, after consultation of the General Assembly and the National Coordinators' Forum, the Executive Director may enter into agreement with third parties, such as e.g. individual institutions and regional authorities in countries that are not a member of RESILIENCE.
2. Institutions from non-member countries or other parties as described in Article 13(1) shall contribute to RESILIENCE ERIC with in cash or in kind resources (e.g. expertise, services, resources, technology knowledge, collaboration opportunities and network).
3. Third parties shall sign an agreement with RESILIENCE ERIC, specifying a certain service/contribution which the party will make, and specify access rights, subscription fee and other conditions in the light of this contribution.

CHAPTER 6

FINANCE

Article 23

Resources

1. The resources of RESILIENCE ERIC shall consist of the following:
 - a. financial contributions of members, observers and individual institutions;
 - b. host contributions;
 - c. other resources within limits and under terms approved by the General Assembly.

Article 24

Budgetary principles, accounts and audit

1. The financial year of RESILIENCE ERIC shall begin on 1 January and end on 31 December of each year.
2. The accounts of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be accompanied by a report on budgetary and financial management of the financial year and a budget forecast for the following financial year.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall be subject to the requirements of the law of the country where it has its statutory seat as regards preparation, filing, auditing and publication of accounts.

Article 25

VAT and excise duty exemption

1. VAT exemptions based on Council Directive 2006/112/EC² and in accordance with Council Implementing Regulation (EU) No 282/2013³ laying down implementing measures for Directive 2006/112/EC and on Council Directive 2008/118/EC⁴ on the general arrangements for products subject to excise duty, shall be limited to purchases by RESILIENCE ERIC of goods and services for the official and exclusive use of RESILIENCE ERIC and made solely for the non-economic activities of RESILIENCE ERIC in line with its activities. VAT and Excise duty exemptions shall be limited to purchases exceeding the value of EUR 250.
2. Excise Duty exemptions based on Article 11 of Council Directive (EU) 2020/262 (Article 12 of Council Directive 2008/118/EC), shall be limited to purchases by RESILIENCE ERIC which are for the official and exclusive use by RESILIENCE ERIC provided that such purchase is made solely for the non-economic activities of RESILIENCE ERIC in line with its activities and that the purchase exceeds the value of EUR 250.
3. Procurement by individual members shall not benefit from these exemptions. No further limits shall apply.

CHAPTER 7

MISCELLANEOUS

Article 26

Working language

The working language of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be English.

Article 27

Location

RESILIENCE ERIC shall be a distributed research infrastructure located in RESILIENCE ERIC member countries, as well as in other countries where RESILIENCE ERIC has concluded agreements in accordance with Article 3.

Article 28

Data Policy

1. Open Source and Open Access principles shall be favoured.
2. RESILIENCE ERIC shall provide guidance (including via website) to users to ensure that research undertaken using material made accessible through RESILIENCE ERIC shall be undertaken within a framework that recognizes the rights of data owners and privacy of individuals.
3. RESILIENCE ERIC shall ensure that users agree to the terms and conditions governing access and that suitable security arrangements are in place regarding internal storage and handling.
4. RESILIENCE ERIC shall define arrangements for investigating allegations of security breaches and confidentiality disclosures regarding research data.

Article 29

Reporting to the European Commission

1. RESILIENCE ERIC shall produce an annual activity report, containing in particular the scientific, operational and financial aspects of its activities. The report shall be approved by the assembly of members and transmitted to the European Commission and relevant public authorities within six months from the end of the corresponding financial year. This report shall be made publicly available.
2. RESILIENCE ERIC shall inform the European Commission of any circumstances which threaten to seriously jeopardise the achievement of RESILIENCE ERIC tasks or hinder RESILIENCE ERIC from fulfilling requirements laid down in Regulation (EC) No 723/2009.

Article 30

Applicable law

1. The internal functioning of RESILIENCE ERIC shall be governed:
 - a. by the European Union law, in particular Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 and the decisions referred to in Articles
 - b. 6(1)(a) and 11(1) of the Regulation;
 - c. by the law of Italy in case of a matter not covered (or only partly covered) by Union law;
 - d. by these statutes.

Article 31

Disputes

1. The Court of Justice of the European Union shall have jurisdiction over litigation among the members in relation to RESILIENCE ERIC, between members and RESILIENCE ERIC and over any litigation to which the Union is a party.

2. Union legislation on jurisdiction shall apply to disputes between RESILIENCE ERIC and third parties. In cases not covered by Union legislation, the law of the State where RESILIENCE ERIC has its statutory seat shall determine the competent jurisdiction for the resolution of such disputes.

Article 32

Statutes updates and availability

1. The Statutes shall be kept up to date and publicly available on RESILIENCE ERIC website and at the statutory seat.
2. The procedure for statutes revision is described in the RESILIENCE ERIC bylaws.

Article 33

Setting-up provisions

1. A first meeting of the General Assembly shall be called by Italy as soon as possible after the Commission decision setting up RESILIENCE ERIC takes effect.
2. Before the first meeting is held and no later than forty-five calendar days after the Commission decision setting up RESILIENCE ERIC takes effect, Italy shall notify the founding Members and Observers of any specific urgent legal action that needs to be taken on behalf of RESILIENCE ERIC.
3. Unless a founding member objects within ten working days after being notified, the legal action shall be carried out by a person duly authorised by the relevant State.

3.1 Annex 1 — List of members, observers and their representing entities

Country or Intergovernmental organisation	Representing entity	Founding member
Albania		
Belgium		
Bosnia&Herzegovina		
Bulgaria		
Cyprus		
France		
Germany		
Georgia		
Greece		
Israel		
Italy		
Poland		
Slovenia		
The Netherlands		

3.2 Annex 2 – Budget contributions

The principles as described below are used to calculate the annual cash contributions by the members and observers that join RESILIENCE ERIC in Year 1 until Year 5, the same principles are applicable. For countries outside Europe the General Assembly may deviate from the principles. By the end of Year 5 the General Assembly shall decide about the calculation method for subsequent periods.

The principles shall be as follows:

Contributions are composed by a flat rate contribution and a GDP-based contribution.

To establish the flat rate contribution, Members are classified into three groups based on their population size (see Table 1 below):

- €10,000 for Members with a population below 5 million (group 1)
- €15,000 for Members with a population between 5,01 and 10 million (group 2)
- €20,000 for Members with a population above 10 million (group 3)

Italy, as host country, adds to the flat rate contribution €50 000.

The amount of the GDP-based contribution is calculated by deducting the overall sum of the flat rate contributions from the total amount of contributions needed.

The GDP-based contribution are based on the country's gross domestic product (GDP) as a percentage of the RESILIENCE Member States GDP. This rounded percentage indicates the number of fee units that a country will pay as GDP-based contribution.

The contribution for each founding member shall be fixed for a period of eight years, with an annual increase of 2 % in order to compensate for increase of costs.

Members joining in later years shall pay the indexed contribution fixed for that year;

Observers shall pay the minimal indexed membership contribution as specified in Table 1 below. Observers do not contribute to the GDP-based contribution.

Individual institutions in non-member countries shall pay the minimal indexed contribution as specified in Table 1 below. Individual institutions in non-member countries do not contribute to the GDP-based contribution.

The contribution for entities joining in the course of a year shall be proportional to the number of remaining months in that year, starting on the first day of the month of joining.

MS/AC	Population (in millions)	Population group	Flat contribution (in K euros)
Albania	2,83	1	10
Belgium	11,68	3	20
Bosnia&Herzegovina	3,21	1	10
Bulgaria	6,68	2	15
Cyprus	1,26	1	10
France	64,75	3	20
Georgia	3,72	1	10
Germany	83,29	3	20
Greece	10,34	3	20
Israel	9,17	2	15
Italy (flat + 50)	58,87	3	70
Netherlands	17,61	3	20
Poland	41,02	3	20
Slovenia	2,11	1	10
TOTAL			270

Table 1 Members flat rate contribution

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CHAPTER 1

VISION AND MISSION

The mission of RESILIENCE is to serve research by improving access to digital as well as physical data on religion and to advanced tools, training, existing research infrastructures and expertise for new, digital, and data-oriented research on religion on a global level.

The field of research on religion has unique characteristics that do not occur (to this extent) in any other field of research. These include:

- The reference of all religions to the numinous, i.e. the presumption of the divine or sacred as a higher and supernatural power outside the worldly sphere. This always remains in the background of all research on religion, despite all strictly scientific treatment.
- The variety of languages and scripts in which the sources are transmitted, including oral and visual traditions.
- The diversity of sources, which include not only texts, but also material (artefacts, architecture, etc.) and immaterial (rites, music, etc.) evidence.
- The difficulty in accessing these diverse sources, often located in religious sites, restricted archives, secluded monuments or other hidden places, and reachable only through personal contacts and networks.
- The integration into complex and often contradictory religious, political and economic discourses that have an effect in synchrony and diachrony.

Acknowledging such a specificity, the ESFRI Roadmap in 2018 (p. 115) stated that « Religious studies have become very relevant not only for researchers, but also social actors and decision makers since positive knowledge on religions is a prerequisite to develop informed dialogue and effective policy in the evolving multicultural society. The economic and demographic crisis affecting Europe, as well as the concurrent immigration from other parts of the world, destabilizes the perception of the European society also in terms of an evolving religious landscape. New forms of orthodoxy appear and social discontent and radicalism are expressed frequently in religious terms which is also a threat to social cohesion in the EU. At the same time, religion has played a central role in social integration throughout the history of humankind and it is important to understand its evolution in a changing European society».

The inclusion of RESILIENCE in the ESFRI Roadmap 2021 demonstrates that RESILIENCE represents an added value in the strengthening and structuring of the European Research Area (ERA) and a significant improvement in the relevant scientific and technological fields at international level (ERIC regulation, Article 4.b).

RESILIENCE picks on the challenge of offering «open access to libraries, archives, human and digital resources, as well as the dedicated services, at a higher level than typically available [today] at the existing

national research centres and laboratories, or at excellence clusters»: to improve knowledge on and understanding of religion RESILIENCE brings together scholars and professionals, and facilities catalyzing new competencies, knowledge, approaches, and impact within the scientific domain of research on religion. It also establishes a system of permanent exchange with users on all levels of research experience and it orients its services strictly to user needs across Europe.

With RESILIENCE, researchers in the many fields of research on religion can profit from the numerous movements of ideas, opportunities and innovations that surround the research community, such as new and more accessible technologies and data shared on the basis of Open Science principles; the adoption of digital tools to strengthen inclusiveness and leverage human interaction; the application of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning solutions to find and produce answers and knowledge, and the most recent trends and evolutions of training and education.

Finally, RESILIENCE is committed to clarity in its objectives and overall goals. To this end, the governance bodies are called to periodically reassess their goals within their team as well as with advisors.

CHAPTER 2

GOVERNANCE

The RESILIENCE RI is conceived as being a distributed structure where the diversity and dynamism of the community of scholars studying religion, the institutions they belong to and the technologies that support their research finds an instrument capable of supporting excellence where it is already established and enhancing valuable innovative ideas where researchers and institutions are in less favorable positions.

Therefore, the RESILIENCE RI governance is foreseen as a light and lean structure that – on the basis of the governance functioning of the ERIC – offers a shared and, European layer and participation opportunities to national nodes – represented by the delegation of their Member State or Associate Country -, to emerging research infrastructures – represented by the delegation of their country as Observer – and to individual institutions willing to contribute but not endorsed by a national delegation – via the National Coordinators Committee.

The functioning and financing of such a structure reflects this vision: along the years, the ERIC will work as a coordinating and governing body a) ensuring to the users access to an infrastructure that is mainly developed and maintained by the different national nodes and b) facilitating connections between and efficiency of the resources, tools and experts distributed in the RESILIENCE infrastructure.

Moreover, RESILIENCE enhances collaboration by constantly reaching out to new potential partners, which are offered several opportunities to contribute to the infrastructure, according to their status, aims and offer.

CHAPTER 3

THE COMMUNITY

RESILIENCE primarily serves the research community of Religious Studies, which is conceived here as the full range of scientific disciplines that enable the study of religion. With its experts and the support to peer-researched, data-oriented knowledge on religion, it also serves societal actors, including religious communities, governments, decision makers, individuals, and institutions.

The community of scholars addressed by RESILIENCE belongs to a wide variety of disciplines and is an expression of geographic, linguistic and economic diversity. Access to data, experts in the field and research institutes is often a challenge for researchers, especially for those in less favorable positions, who can be hampered in conducting excellent research. To address these challenges, RESILIENCE structures the delivery of its services in a way that recognises the capabilities of its facilities and national nodes while keeping a strong overarching role in defining the priorities at a higher level.

The results and feedback that stem from the launching of a starting community, RelReS – Research Infrastructure for Religious Studies and of EuARe – European Academy of Religion, strengthened by the track record of participation in additional projects and initiatives as the main players for the community and the activities conducted following an enlargement strategy that takes into account the variety of disciplines involved and data used in the study of religion testify to the need for such a community of a pan-European research infrastructure that is able to:

- a) establish and maintain a veritable critical mass of institutions, capable of substantially reframing the field of research on religions towards a less fragmented and more globalised approach to research;
- b) address the necessity to substantially increase the level of networking among all subjects involved in the study of religion to become more publicly recognizable and to demonstrate the relevance, potential, capabilities, and competences of the expertise available in the different fields of the domain in order to support the European knowledge-based methodology to deal with religious pluralism;
- c) address the need to offer the community of scholars studying religion a structured system of access to sources, resources and facilities, which can boost excellence in research.

RESILIENCE is necessary for the carrying-out of European research programmes and projects, including for the efficient execution of Community research, technological development and demonstration programmes (ERIC regulation, Article 4.a).

CHAPTER 4

THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE (DATA, EXPERTS, TOOLS)

RESILIENCE is composed of a digital environment and a physical network of facilities whose size, mission and role may vary according to their specificities. The RI has always been and is enriched by such a variety of institutions, which offers a good balance of management flexibility, professional experience, operational complexity and scientific competence: RESILIENCE especially connects institutions and facilities which have

a strong competence and experience with digital and data-oriented research methods and which have rich resources for research on religion.

The RESILIENCE environment and network strive for open and FAIR access to digital and physical resources from Europe and beyond and offers researchers the use of valuable distributed data, tools, expertise, training, and services via a single point of access (virtual) as well as by discovering collections and having meetings with experts through on-site visits.

The service offer is driven by the users' needs and the ability of the RESILIENCE RI to innovate and anticipate such needs: even if strongly committed towards the usage of tested and cutting edge information technologies, already existing tools, research outcomes and outputs, RESILIENCE creates new methods, instruments, tools and services to better support research on religion and stimulates the usage of new technologies in research on religion.

Moreover, as the community of researchers studying religion deals with sources that will never be digitized and whose digitization limits the research development, RESILIENCE is committed to support with dedicated initiatives physical access to the resources made available through the infrastructure, like the Trans-National Access Programme, which is one of the RESILIENCE core services and is key to contribute to the mobility of knowledge and/or researchers within the ERA and increases the use of intellectual potential throughout Europe (ERIC regulation, Article 4.d).

The RIs activities and developments, as well as the opportunities it offers are presented to the community according to a communication plan, enabling the research community and other stakeholders to learn about the RI and the community's research initiatives. The RI positions such a role at the core of its structure and manages communication, dissemination and exploitation activities at the headquarters, with the aim of contributing to the dissemination and optimisation of the results of activities in Community research, technological development and demonstration (ERIC regulation, Article 4.e).

The typology of entities that is part of the RESILIENCE RI includes:

- Libraries, archives, galleries, and museums
- Research centers
- Universities, their Departments and Faculties
- Computing and data centers

Since RESILIENCE is a **distributed RI**, it is to be organised around a central hub that coordinates a network of services that are delivered through **national nodes**. We identified four service types:

- Core Services managed by either RESILIENCE headquarters or members;
- Community (in-kind) Services contributed by national nodes;
- Internal Services which are essential for the operation of the RI but not part of the public service catalogue.

Besides contributing to the service catalogue, the national nodes have the responsibility to establish and grow a collaborative local network, identify user needs, contribute national data and expertise, facilitate engagement and communication with the local community and align with other national research consortia.

Following this purpose, RESILIENCE fosters a service catalogue that is accessible and findable, allowing end-users to fully understand each service's readiness, benefits, and limitations. It is important for the catalogue to constantly evolve as to remain relevant to the SSH community. These updates need to be informed by user needs, market trends, and innovative developments within the research community. The following guiding principles support the establishment of the priorities of the RESILIENCE service catalogue.

1. RESILIENCE services should be driven by expertise and excellence

RESILIENCE should offer services in which the community can boast both expertise and excellence in the study of religion. For other services in which we hold only circumstantial expertise, RESILIENCE could look towards collaborations with e-infrastructures (e.g., EUDAT) and other RI providers in the SSH cluster and beyond. The EOSC will be a valuable additional source of services for researchers in need of technology. RESILIENCE can help researchers find the right service in the wider offering of e-infrastructures and RI providers. By stimulating and coordinating a bidirectional input flow between user and service provider, RESILIENCE will boost the quality of research and services alike.

2. RESILIENCE services should safeguard that our community's research output is both FAIR and sustainable

When RESILIENCE hosts research outputs such as research data, websites, blogs or software, we should be able to guarantee that resources are and remain Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) over time (or for the minimum period indicated in a clear and transparent service description). This requires a mature service level with a stable and robust infrastructure and a strong support team in place. This is necessary to prevent the loss of digital objects and thus the trust of our community who have put the safeguarding of their intellectual work into our hands. As a result, RESILIENCE should consider working with trusted and sustainable depositing solutions when possible or adhere to the expected requirements for a trustworthy repository when no existing solutions are available.

3. RESILIENCE should be transparent about its service offerings

The service catalogue can contain innovative new services and tools that have a low Technology / Service Readiness Level (T/SRL). It is however important to offer potential users clear information on the experimental and possibly temporary nature of the service. Users should be able to export their research data in an open and interoperable data format to prevent data loss. Transparency about the T/SRL allows RESILIENCE to offer valuable innovative and experimental tools to the community without risking critique on quality and long-term availability of the service offering.

4. RESILIENCE services should have a clear and concrete service description

RESILIENCE should provide clear and concrete service descriptions, so users immediately understand what the service entails, what to expect (e.g. T/SRL), how they will benefit, what its added value is, what the modalities of access are, and more. Service information should be findable through the RESILIENCE service

catalogue, accessible via the RESILIENCE website and distributed to other service discovery platforms such as the SSH Open Marketplace and the EOSC.

5. RESILIENCE services should be stakeholder-driven and follow market and digital innovations

The RESILIENCE service catalogue should evolve over time by innovative input coming from researchers, developers, service providers, and projects alike. It should also follow market trends and digital innovations to remain state-of-the-art and relevant. This could be achieved, for example, by establishing a dedicated trends/innovation discovery team to actively monitor digital as well as societal evolutions (e.g. influence of fake news on data validity, switch towards video “reels” communication).

6. RESILIENCE services should be findable and accessible for the end-users

RESILIENCE services, once promoted to the community, should be easily findable via search engines, the RESILIENCE website, and the future RESILIENCE service catalogue. They should:

- Include a clear and standardised service description and value proposition.
- Provide transparency on their T/SRL and mode of access (e.g., short/long term, selection only, paid access).
- Be accessible via a persistent link to the service/tool/database which has a minimum T/SRL of 4, and provides supporting documentation as well as contact information (e.g. helpdesk).

The RESILIENCE Service Catalogue should focus on services that are findable and accessible for users with a minimum TRL of 4. This ensures that users are only given access to tools and services that are reliable and sustainable. Given that research projects typically last up to 4 years, it is crucial that researchers have access to tools available within their project timeframe. Additionally, the rapid evolution of our (digital) society means some services may change providers or become obsolete by 2025 because of changing user needs. Since the service catalogue targets end-user (researcher) audiences specifically, services in their ideation phase (TRL 0-3) should not be promoted in the catalogue at this stage, except for a brief mention of future ideas. Components essential for the functioning and interoperability of the RI but not directly relevant to our end-users, such as email, security or Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), should also not be included.

7. RESILIENCE services should be integrated into the wider SSH and EOSC ecosystem

RESILIENCE should strive early on towards interoperability and integration of services into the SSH Open Marketplace, EOSC EU Node and Federation of Nodes. This will increase the visibility as well as demonstrate the quality and maturity of the service offering. RESILIENCE should also consider the interfacing with, and integration and adaptation of relevant services and tools developed by other communities to meet its users’ needs. Most relevant to watch and collaborate with are other SSH communities such as DARIAH, CLARIN and CESSDA, with an open view towards initiatives and innovations happening in other science domains. These integrations ensure that resources can also be discovered and used outside of the communities where they originated. To facilitate future integration, RESILIENCE service descriptions will align with established metadata schemes, categorizations and standards used by established infrastructures like EOSC and

SSHOC. This alignment ensures that our services remain compatible and easily integrable with evolving platforms and policies, maintaining their relevance and accessibility.

8. RESILIENCE should offer core services that serve a wide user base

RESILIENCE should prioritise the development of services that are valuable to a wide user base. Core services:

- can be developed and hosted by partners but preferably enjoy some sort of central support,
- should comply to a quality service level and include clear communication towards the Board of Directors (BoD) and the General Assembly (GenA) concerning the status, continuity, and development roadmap of the service,
- should be transferable to another hosting location/organisation,
- should be clearly branded as RESILIENCE.

The RESILIENCE service strategy should be driven by user demand, fed by regular user consultations in combination with trend monitoring in the research- and wider digital market space. This continuous input means that core services will evolve over time. To meet the ever changing needs of our community, RESILIENCE can decide to integrate other decentralised (in-kind) services into their core facility in consultation with the original service owner and the community. This can for example happen when a large user base and high value for the community have been clearly demonstrated. RESILIENCE might also decide to start new development trajectories when certain gaps in the service catalogue must be addressed to serve the specific needs of our user community.

9. RESILIENCE node services can be locally driven

Services developed by partners using (partial) RESILIENCE EU funding should be clearly branded as RESILIENCE and comply with the criteria of core services (cf. guiding principle 8). As several in-kind services will (have) be(en) developed outside the context of RESILIENCE (e.g. digitization lab of a university library), they can have their own branding and decision structure. However, for their inclusion in the RESILIENCE service catalogue, they need to comply to a certain quality level if we want the in-kinds to be of true value to our users. Preferably their TRL is minimum a 7, though pilot demonstrators can be included as long as the TRL is clearly indicated to the end users.

CHAPTER 5

THE TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The technical infrastructure is designed around the following principles:

User-Centric Design: Services are tailored to meet the specific needs of researchers in religious studies, ensuring ease of use, high performance, and flexibility.

Sustainability, Scalability, and Security: Services are built to grow with increasing research needs, ensuring long-term sustainability through secure and scalable access and functionality.

Compliance with Open Science and Research Policies: Services comply with Open Science, FAIR data principles, and GDPR, supporting transparency, reproducibility, and long-term accessibility of research outputs.

Maturity and Robustness: The IT services demonstrate high Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 9) to ensure reliability. They integrate with the broader research ecosystem, enabling seamless collaboration and access to computational, storage, and network resources.

Alignment with EU Green ICT Objectives: In line with the EU's commitment to green digital transformation, the IT services prioritize energy efficiency, sustainable data management, and eco-friendly practices. This includes promoting energy-efficient digital infrastructures, exploring low power computing solutions, and supporting sustainable practices across data centers and cloud services.

The mapping conducted on already existing services enabling access to physical and electronic infrastructures that are relevant for the RESILIENCE RI shows that RESILIENCE can leverage existing resources like CINECA, EGI, EURO HPC and EOSC EU Node to avoid the need for purchasing physical hardware. This approach ensures scalability and flexibility while aligning with modern scientific standards such as Open Science and FAIR data.

Additionally, the mapping highlights what are the already existing services that can be exploited for the following:

- Instruments & Equipment Access
- Computing Resources
- Data Storage Solutions
- Virtualization
- Security & Operations
- Security & Identity Management
- Operations & Infrastructure Management
- Service Integration and Interoperability

and how RESILIENCE should approach Service Onboarding and Evolution and Aggregators and Integrators.

CHAPTER 6

NATIONAL CONSORTIA

Each member of the RESILIENCE General Assembly is called to structure the national facilities and infrastructures into a National consortium expressing one representative that seats in the National Coordinators Committee and has the responsibility of a) coordinating local and national projects with the

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ERIC European initiatives, in agreement with the Executive Director; b) promoting the access to the research infrastructure by the national community.

The collaboration between national consortia and the RESILIENCE ERIC is key to grants effective access, in accordance with the rules established in its statutes, to the European research community, composed of researchers from Member States and from associated countries. Modalities of access are expressed in the access policy included in the ERIC statutes, and explicated in the TNA Services Management Plan and in the Service Preparation and Implementation Strategy (ERIC regulation, Article 4.c).

5 Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792

6 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	03/2025	ERIC Practical Guidelines: Legal Framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium
R2	28/11/2024	D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy
R3	21/09/2020	D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy (GA. 871127)
R4	02/08/2024	D1.3 Financial and Sustainability Plan
R5	30/06/2021	D2.4 RESILIENCE Design Study Report (GA n. 871127)
R6	25/11/2024	D4.2 Communication Dissemination & Exploitation Plan
R13	11/01/2024	RESILIENCE Vision and Mission Statement

